

EXOPLANETS IDENTIFICATION AND CLUSTERING WITH MACHINE LEARNING METHODS

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ABSTRACT

The discovery of habitable exoplanets has long been a heated topic in astronomy. Traditional methods for exoplanet identification include the wobble method, direct imaging, gravitational microlensing, etc., which not only require a considerable investment of manpower, time, and money, but also are limited by the performance of astronomical telescopes. In this study, we proposed the idea of using machine learning methods to identify exoplanets. We used the Kepler dataset collected by NASA from the Kepler Space Observatory to conduct supervised learning, which predicts the existence of exoplanet candidates as a three-categorical classification task, using decision tree, random forest, naïve Bayes, and neural network; we used another NASA dataset consisted of the confirmed exoplanets data to conduct unsupervised learning, which divides the confirmed exoplanets into different clusters, using k-means clustering. As a result, our models achieved accuracies of 99.06%, 92.11%, 88.50%, and 99.79%, respectively, in the supervised learning task and successfully obtained reasonable clusters in the unsupervised learning task.

KEYWORDS

Exoplanets Identification and Clustering, Kepler Dataset, Classification Tree, Random Forest, Naïve Bayes, Multi-layer Perceptron, K-means Clustering, K-fold Cross-validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, astronomers around the world have been relentlessly seeking for habitable exoplanets (planets outside the Solar System) with great interest [1]. Some habitable exoplanet candidates are Kepler-22b, which is 600 light-years away from the Sun with an orbital period of 290 days, that has a possible rocky surface at a temperature of approximately 295K with an active atmosphere [2]; Kepler-69c, which is 2,700 light-years away from the Sun with an orbital period of 242 days, that is of super-earth-sized with a smaller gravity of 7.159 m/s², compared to the earth's gravity [3]; Kepler-442b, which is 1,194 light-years away from the Sun with an orbital period of 112 days, that is within the habitable zone of its solar system [4].

How can astronomers discover these exoplanets? The answer is they have devoted a considerable amount of time, energy, and money to explore the vast universe with specialized equipment, such as the astronomical telescope. As a result, astronomers collect observed data for further analysis, while the identification of a potential exoplanet remains a complicated problem. How can we confirm an observation from some astronomical telescopes is an existent exoplanet but not a false positive sample?

There are several traditional exoplanet identification techniques, including the wobble method, direct imaging, gravitational microlensing, etc. Specifically, the wobble method traces exoplanets via a Doppler shift in the star's light frequencies caused by its planets; direct imaging uses extra-terrestrial telescopes to capture images from exoplanets; gravitational microlensing detects the

distortion of the background light [5]. These traditional methods are expensive, time-consuming, and sensitive to variation in the measurement. Based on these limitations, our motivation for this study is to develop a simple, efficient, and economic approach to identify exoplanets. Therefore, we proposed the idea of using machine learning methods for the identification of exoplanets and used two datasets, both were collected by NASA, to conduct a three-categorical classification task (supervised learning) and a clustering task (unsupervised learning).

For the supervised learning task, we used the Kepler dataset consisted of false positive (labelled as “-1”), candidate (labelled as “0”), and confirmed (labelled as “1”) exoplanet samples to perform a three-categorical classification. The objective is to achieve a classification accuracy of more than 95%. We selected and trained four models for this problem: classification tree, random forest, naïve Bayes, and neural network. As a result, our models achieved accuracies of 99.06%, 92.11%, 88.50%, and 99.79%, respectively.

For the unsupervised learning task, we used another dataset consisted of the confirmed exoplanets data to do the clustering. The objective is to find exoplanets that are in the same cluster as the earth. We selected and trained a k-means model for this problem. As a result, our k-means model partitioned reasonable clusters, and we visualized all exoplanets in the same cluster as the earth in a star map.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II summarizes the related work from other researchers. Before the modelling and inference, we conducted data cleaning, exploratory data analysis (EDA), feature selection, etc., and these are written in Section III. In Section IV, we present the detailed experimental setup, including model optimization and optimal parameters. Section V analyses the results obtained by our models and discusses the meanings of the results. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper with the significance of this study and future work to be done.

2. RELATED WORK

NASA’s Kepler Mission devoted years of effort to discover exoplanets. William J. Borucki [6] summarized how traditional approaches were used in the real-world scientific research to confirm, validate, and model the discovered exoplanets by Kepler. Natalie M. Batalha [7] stated that the progress made by the Kepler Mission indicates there are orbiting systems that might potentially be habitable places for the human beings. Lissauer et al. [8] emphasized the contribution made by the Kepler Mission and the significance of its data in exoplanets detection.

Based on the Kepler dataset or other similar datasets, there are studies that combine machine learning methods with exoplanets detection, identification, and analysis. Christopher J. Shallue and Andrew Vanderburg [9] used a convolutional neural network to process the astrophysical signals and validated two new exoplanets according to the CNN predictions. Rohan Saha [10] implemented logistic regression, decision tree, and neural network on the Kepler dataset to find out the probability of existence of an exoplanet candidate. Maldonado et al. [11] summarized studies about exoplanet transit discovery with ML-based algorithms. Fisher et al. [12] interpreted high-resolution spectroscopy of exoplanets with cross-correlations and supervised learning such as Bayesian neural networks. Basak et al. [13] constructed novel neural network architectures to explore the habitability classification of exoplanets.

These related studies provided us with precious insights into the data pre-processing, model training, selection, and inference procedures. We designed our experiment based on these studies and used some of their results as benchmarks.

3. DATA PRE-PROCESSING

In this section, we introduce the data pre-processing procedures involved in this study and a short description of the datasets.

3.1. Dataset Description

The first dataset (the Kepler dataset) in this study is collected by NASA from the Kepler Space Observatory. In 2009, NASA launched the Kepler Mission, an effort to discover exoplanets with the goal of finding potentially habitable places for human beings [14]. The mission lasted for over nine years with remarkable legacies—a total number of 9,564 potential exoplanets are contained in the Kepler dataset, each associated with features that indicate the characteristics of the detected “exoplanet”.

Among these features, there is a categorical variable which we selected as the target variable, *koi_disposition*, with three possible values, “CONFIRMED” (labelled as “1”), “CANDIDATE” (labelled as “0”), and “FALSE POSITIVE” (labelled as “-1”). If an exoplanet is “CONFIRMED”, its existence has been confirmed, and is associated with a name recorded by *kepler_name* variable; if an exoplanet is “CANDIDATE”, its existence has not been proven yet; if an exoplanet is “FALSE POSITIVE”, it has been proven a false positive observation. There are totally 2,358 confirmed exoplanets, 2,366 candidate exoplanets, and the rest 4,840 exoplanets are false positive. We used the Kepler dataset for classification, the supervised learning task.

The second dataset (the confirmed exoplanets dataset) contains stellar and planetary parameters of the confirmed exoplanets [15]. These observations are worldwide, not solely from the Kepler Mission. Crucial parameters include radius, mass, density, temperature, etc. There are totally 4,375 confirmed exoplanets in this dataset, some were originally discovered by the Kepler Space Observatory, the rest were originally found by other space observatories. We used the confirmed exoplanets dataset for clustering, the unsupervised learning task.

3.2. Data Cleaning

The first step of data cleaning was to calculate the proportion of empty entries in each column. We excluded columns with a large proportion of empty data. Then columns with a small fraction of empty data were manually selected and the empty entries in the preserved columns were filled with proper values. Finally, some data were dropped if they had empty values after data cleaning.

3.3. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

Before feature selection and model construction, exploratory data analysis (EDA) is necessary to facilitate the data analysis process and make it easier and more precise [16]. In this study, EDA was carried out to obtain an intuitive and high-level understanding of the datasets.

3.3.1. Correlation Analysis

We first conducted correlation analysis to identify highly correlated variables and reduce data redundancy and collinearity. The correlation matrices of the two datasets are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Both the x-axis and y-axis of Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 are features, and the entry values represent the correlation coefficients between pairs of features. These two figures are symmetric, because the correlation coefficient between a variable X and another variable Y follows $Corr(X, Y) = Corr(Y, X)$. In addition, the diagonal from top left to bottom right is solely consisted of 1's, since

for each variable X , $Corr(X, X) = 1$. For a pair of variables, the larger the correlation coefficient is, the higher the collinearity is; therefore, features with one or more high correlation coefficients were eliminated by us.

Figure 1. Correlation Matrix of the Kepler Dataset

Figure 2. Correlation Matrix of the Confirmed Exoplanets Dataset

3.3.2. Univariate Analysis

Then univariate analysis was performed to visualize the distribution of each variable.

Figure 3. Count Plots of the Binary Variables of the Kepler Dataset

Figure 4. Histogram of the Log Scale Orbital Periods of the Kepler Dataset

Fig. 3 shows the count of each binary variable in the Kepler dataset, which gives the distribution of four binary characteristics (non-transit-like, stellar eclipse, centroid offset, ephemeris match indicates contamination) of the exoplanet candidates.

Fig. 4. is a histogram that indicates the relationship between an important feature, the log scale orbital period, and the target variable. From Fig. 4, the confirmed exoplanets follow a Gaussian distribution with respect to the log scale orbital period in the range between -2 and 4. If the value of the log scale orbital period is too high or too low, the candidate is more likely to be a false positive observation.

3.3.3. Bivariate Analysis

Finally, we used bivariate analysis to investigate the pairwise relationship between different features and observe how they affect the target variable.

Fig. 5 is a star map of the exoplanet candidates. In this star map, each pair of celestial coordinates is measured by right ascension (RA), the celestial coordinate that represents longitude, and declination (Dec), the celestial coordinate that represents latitude [17]. Fig. 5 demonstrates that there is no strong correlation between the target variable and coordinates, because for every target value, there is no clear cluster of exoplanets shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 6 is a categorical plot of the log scale orbital period versus number of planets in the exoplanet candidate's solar system. The result shows that false positive samples are most likely to

have just one or two planets in their solar system. With a higher number of planets in a candidate's solar system, the probability of it being a real exoplanet is also higher.

Figure 5. Star Map by Right Ascension (RA) and Declination (Dec)

Figure 6. Categorical Plot of the Log Scale Orbital Period versus Number of Planets

3.4. Feature Selection

Based on the correlation heatmaps, we excluded variables that have high correlation coefficients with one or more other input features or have a low correlation coefficient with the target variable. For example, variables that store the deviation of observations, such as `koi_period_err` (error of the orbital period) and `koi_time0_err` (error of the transit epoch), are highly dependent on the observed values (orbital period and transit epoch). Therefore, we just kept variables that store the observed values but abandoned variables that record deviation. Some preserved features are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Examples of Preserved Features after Feature Selection

Variable	Dataset	Meaning	Description
<code>kepler_name</code>	Kepler	Kepler Name	Kepler name in the form of “Kepler-” plus a number and a lower-case letter (e. g. Kepler-22b, Kepler-186f)
<code>koi_fpflag_nt</code>	Kepler	Non-Transit-Like Flag	1 means the light curve is not consistent with that of a transiting planet
<code>koi_period</code>	Kepler	Orbital Period	Measured in days and is taken in log scale
<code>koi_count</code>	Kepler	Number of Planets	Number of exoplanet candidates identified in a solar system
<code>pl_radj</code>	Confirmed Exoplanets	Planet Radius	Measured in Jupiter Radius
<code>pl_bmassj</code>	Confirmed Exoplanets	Planet Mass	Measured in Jupiter Mass
<code>sy_dist</code>	Confirmed Exoplanets	Distance	Distance to the planetary system in parsecs

4. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this section, we discuss the model training process in detail with optimization and parameters. The training process was divided into two parts, training models for classification, and training the k-means model for clustering. For these two parts, we used the Kepler dataset and confirmed exoplanets dataset, respectively. For the supervised learning task, we used decision tree, random forest, naïve Bayes, and neural network. For the unsupervised learning task, we used k-means clustering.

4.1. Classification Tree

The reason why we chose the decision tree model is that it can split data with classification rules based on the highest information gain, $Info\ Gain = Entropy_{parent} - Entropy_{children}$. In a classification tree model, each internal node represents a sample to be split, and each leaf node represents a class label, or prediction.

We implemented the classification tree model using `DecisionTreeClassifier` from scikit-learn library and optimized its performance with different parameters. We set the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node from 2 to 100 and maximum depth of the tree from 1 to 20, then we selected the parameters that maximized accuracy. As a result, the optimal minimum number of samples required to split an internal node is 53 and maximum depth of the tree is 7. Finally, we visualized the optimal decision tree using `Graphviz`. The optimal decision tree is shown in Fig. 7 in the next section.

4.2. Random Forest

Random forest combines multiple decision trees together at the training time. As a result, these decision trees form an ensemble which predicts the class category using the label with the most votes. For example, in a random forest of 9 decision trees, if 6 predict 1, then the random forest outputs 1. Customized rules might be applied to break the tie.

We implemented the random forest model using RandomForestRegressor from scikit-learn library. We optimized the number of trees in the forest by setting this parameter from 20 to 1000 with a step size of 20. As a result, the highest accuracy was obtained when the number of trees is 40.

4.3. Naïve Bayes

Naïve Bayes applies Bayes' theorem under the assumption that features are independent. It's a simple probabilistic approach to conduct the classification task. For features X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n and classes C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m , $Naïve\ Bayes(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \underset{c}{\operatorname{argmax}} p(C = c) \prod_{i=1}^n p(X_i = x_i | C = c)$.

We implemented the naïve Bayes model using ComplementNB from scikit-learn library. Before training the naïve Bayes classifier, we standardized input features, encoded the target variable as a one-hot vector, and set each prior as the proportion of each class in the sample space.

4.4. Multilayer Perceptron

Neural network is another machine learning model that is widely used in classification problems. In a neural network, each layer has an activation function that receives the output values from the previous layer and outputs values calculated by the activation function. For each set of features, the final prediction of the neural network is the output of its last layer.

We implemented the neural network model using MLPRegressor from scikit-learn library. We tried three activation functions, logistic, tanh, and ReLU. These activation functions determine how the weighted sum of the input to the current layer is converted into the output to the next layer. We also chose three types of solvers, stochastic gradient descent, quasi-Newton method, and Adam optimizer. Finally, we optimized the layer size and learning rate. The optimal neural network uses tanh as the activation function and Adam as the optimizer with a layer size of 25 and a learning rate of 0.003.

4.5. K-Means Clustering

K-means is a classic unsupervised learning algorithm for clustering problems. It partitions data into k clusters with the objective of minimizing the sum of distance of each sample to its cluster centroid in a repeated way.

We aimed at discovering which exoplanets are in the same group as the earth. In this way, we might find potentially habitable places for human beings. We implemented the k-means model using KMeans from scikit-learn library. We set the number of clusters as 100.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

For the classification problem, the decision tree achieved an accuracy of 99.06%, random forest achieved an accuracy of 92.11%, naïve Bayes achieved an accuracy of 88.50%, and multilayer

perceptron achieved an accuracy of 99.79%. These four models all performed well on the test set, as each achieved a high classification accuracy.

We further evaluated the performance of these models with 10-fold cross-validation, a resampling method that tests if a model generalizes well, using KFold from scikit-learn library. As a result, the random forest model achieved the best average accuracy of 82.39%.

Figure 7. The Optimal Classification Tree Obtained

We visualized the classification tree with the highest accuracy using Graphviz and plotted the importance of each feature. The optimal classification tree obtained is shown in Fig. 7 and the importance of each feature is shown in Fig. 8 and Table 2. From Fig. 7, Fig. 8, and Table 2, the most important feature is stellar eclipse, a flag variable indicating if some phenomena caused by an eclipsing binary are observed, with a Gini importance score of 0.30512. The most important continuous variable is the log scale orbital period measured in days, with a Gini importance score of 0.05115.

Figure 8. The Importance Scores of Features in the Kepler Dataset

Table 2. Kepler Feature List with Variable Name, Importance, Meaning, and Description

Variable	Importance	Meaning	Description
koi_fpflag_ss	0.30512	Stellar Eclipse	1 means some phenomena caused by an eclipsing binary observed
koi_fpflag_co	0.27971	Centroid Offset	1 means the source of the signal is from a nearby star
koi_fpflag_nt	0.27158	Non-Transit-Like	1 means the light curve is not consistent with that of a transiting planet
koi_period	0.05115	Orbital Period	Measured in days and is taken in log scale
koi_count	0.03464	Number of Planets	Number of exoplanet candidates identified in a solar system
koi_fpflag_ec	0.03245	Ephemeris Match Indicates Contamination	1 means the candidate shares the same period and epoch as another object
koi_time0	0.01978	Transit Epoch	Measured in Barycentric Julian Day (BJD)

Finally, we visualized the exoplanets in the same cluster as the earth in Fig. 9. As a result, these exoplanets are most likely to be habitable for human beings. For example, HD 7924 d, HD 33564 b, HD 17156 b, GJ 96 b, Teegarden’s Star b are among these exoplanets. There are totally 39 exoplanets in the same cluster as the earth.

and the precision-recall curves to understand the diagnostic ability of different machine learning models. McNamara's test can also be applied to compare different algorithms [10]. Finally, the discussion of statistical significance tests and execution time can be included in model evaluation.

People from different cultures may connect to the concept of a "planet" as follows, they live on one, our mother earth, view the moon shared by all human beings, and learn the names of the other planets in our solar system from an early age. Planets that circle the star, rather than nebulae or galaxies, are easier to fit into our shared cultural view of the universe. For us, exoplanet exploration bridges the heaven with human consciousness and opens a vast exploration area to look forward to—seeking other habitable worlds. Finally, it has increased the likelihood that our long-term study points toward, we are not alone in the universe.

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